

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A3.1.1

**Literature review of the methodologies used for assessing the representativeness of sampling for
both gaseous species and particulates at HD HRS**

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Submission date of the deliverable/report: 22nd of November 2023

Revision date of the deliverable/report: -

Summary

Sampling always leads to some degree of error unless the entire population is analyzed. A representative sample should be an unbiased reflection of the gas to analyse i.e., it shall have the same composition as the gas it is attributed to. The assumption is that the collected samples both accurately and precisely represent the gas to be analysed. However, demonstrating that the sample taken is representative of a lot is complex. This report discusses the term representativeness and presents a methodology to assess sample representativeness, which is not based of statistical analysis of the data after the fact. In summary, representativeness is considered as a concept and not quantifiable.

In this report, the most relevant information from the Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide on measurement uncertainty arising from sampling are summarized. Two main contributions to the sampling uncertainty needs to be assessed: the sampling precision (due to random errors) and the sampling bias (due to systematic errors). In contrary to sample representativeness, measurement uncertainty is a quantitative notion.

Two main approaches to uncertainty estimation arising from sampling are described the empirical approach which uses some level of replication of the whole measurement procedure to give a direct estimate of the uncertainty for the final result of the measurement, and the modelling approach which identifies all of the sources of uncertainty, quantifies the contributions from each source, and then combines all of the contributions, as a budget, to give an estimate of the combined standard uncertainty.

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1 Introduction

Sampling (designing the sampling plan, taking the samples, making decisions from the results) is critical in the measurement process. The determination of gas composition, impurity concentration and physical properties depend, to a large extent, on sampling technique. The use of correct sampling techniques is an important safety and quality critical step in gas analysis [1]. There is, however, always some degree of sampling error unless the entire population is analyzed. Since analysis of an entire lot of interest is typically cost prohibitive or impractical, a sample (a portion) is taken from the lot in order to make estimations about the characteristics of that lot (lot is the total amount of material from which a sample is taken). In the case of hydrogen fuel, taking a large or the whole sample also implies wasting a lot of fuel that would have otherwise been distributed to end users. It is therefore unreasonable to analyse the entire sample. Sampling and sample representativeness assumes that the sample taken will represent the population and therefore extracting only a portion of the fuel delivered should be sufficient. This assumption has another implication regarding the minimum size of the sample needed to fulfil the representativeness and relies on the homogeneity of the sample. However, the demonstration that the sample taken is representative of a lot is complex, especially with a dynamic process that may require to sample along at specific times.

A representative sample should be an unbiased reflection of the gas to be analysed i.e., it shall have the same composition as the gas it is attributed to. The assumption is that the collected samples both accurately and precisely represent the gas to be analysed. Without special attention to that assumption, sampling could be the weakest link leading to the largest errors in the measurement process or the experimental study [2]. A representative sample is established by two main criteria [3]:

- a) The sample is not altered in any way, or more realistically in any avoidable way, during the process of collecting, handling, containing or preparing the sample for analysis or measurement.
- b) The sample is taken at a sample point where we can be sure that it is actually from the bulk to which the information is to be applied at a known time or time period.

Representativeness of samples (field and laboratory) is therefore a function of sampling error. If no sampling error exists, the samples would by definition be representative [4].

The uncertainty associated with sampling is a product of both the sample (physical and chemical attributes) and the sampling process (involving statistical issues and sampling technique). [2]

Considerations must be given about the degree of heterogeneity of the material being sampled, the methods used for sample collection (including what proper tools to use), what it is that the sample is supposed to represent, the mass (sample support) of the sample needed to be representative, and the bounds of what “representative” actually means.

It is now mandatory for the implementation of ISO 14687 [5] to control that the validation requirements set in ISO 21087 [6] are met. Only in this case, the methods can be considered as fit-for-purpose for hydrogen purity testing. The validation parameters to be assessed include limit of detection, working range, selectivity, precision, trueness and measurement uncertainty. According to ISO21087, the relative combined uncertainty at concentrations close to the threshold value should be below 10% of the concentration for amount fraction equal or above 10 nmol/mol. For some compounds, it seems that this

value is difficult to meet in practice (for example a stability study performed during 19ENG04 MetroHyve2 showed that the analytical uncertainty for HCl around the threshold seemed close to 50%). The standard only considers analytical methods. However, sampling uncertainties contributes to the overall uncertainty of the measurement.

To obtain the required uncertainty (which makes the measurements fit for purpose), evaluation of the sampling and analytical procedures proposed to meet those purposes must be undertaken.

One of the important documents regarding the measurement uncertainty arising from sampling is the Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide on this topic [7]. The aim of this Guide is to explain the rationale, and practical application, of the methods available for the estimation of uncertainty that include the contribution from sampling. It is intended for specialists such as sampling planners and for analytical chemists who need to estimate the uncertainty associated with their measurement results.

The following section summarizes important information from this guide.

2 Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide “Measurement uncertainty arising from sampling”

According to the Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest guide [7] which is the main guide for metrologists related to sampling uncertainties, sampling theory has developed largely independently of analytical chemistry and chemical metrology. Sampling quality has generally been addressed by the selection of a ‘correct’ sampling protocol, appropriate validation, and training of sampling personnel to ensure that this protocol is applied correctly [7]. If all the above are fulfilled, it is then assumed that the taken samples will be representative and unbiased. An approach more consistent with the rest of the measurement process is to estimate the uncertainty of sampling for typical materials, or for sampling targets, during validation of the sampling protocol, and to confirm compliance in practice using ongoing quality control. The guide provides methodologies to quantify the uncertainty that arises when a given protocol is used.

There are two main approaches to uncertainty estimation arising from sampling, these methods also apply to any measurement:

- 1) The empirical approach (also called experimental, retrospective or top down) which has the widest applicability to the broadest range of measurement systems and applications (e.g. gaseous, liquid and solid)
- 2) The modelling approach (also called theoretical, predictive or bottom up) which is used in particular situations (e.g., particulate solids)

The combination of these different approaches can be used to give more reliable, and cost-effective estimates of uncertainty in a range of measurement systems.

The empirical approach uses some level of replication of the whole measurement procedure to give a direct estimate of the uncertainty for the final result of the measurement, without necessarily knowing any of the sources individually.

The modelling approach identifies all of the sources of uncertainty, quantifies the contributions from each source, and then combines all of the contributions, as a budget, to give an estimate of the combined

standard uncertainty. This approach well established for analytical methods can also be applied to the process of sampling. The principal advantage of the modelling approach is that it allows the largest source of uncertainty to be readily identified.

The applicability of the two approaches varies between the different materials to be sampled. In the EURACHEM guide, the empirical method which is applicable to gaseous, liquid and solid samples is described in detail, while the modelling approach is only described in particular situations (e.g., particulate solids).

2.1 Empirical approach

The principal advantage of the modelling approach is that it allows the largest source of uncertainty to be readily identified.

The empirical approach relies on repetitive realisation and on the variance observed in real sampling. It did not provide any information on the exact technical source of the uncertainty (i.e., issues with heterogeneity or pressure). Therefore, it is difficult to resolve or improve the uncertainty due to the lack of knowledge on the real sources of it. On the other hand, it often provides a conservative estimation of the uncertainty due to its empirical determination through testing. The main drawback is its reliance on experiments which requires significant efforts and resources to determine it.

There are four sources contributing to the uncertainty:

- 1) Random errors arising from the sampling (called sampling precision)
- 2) Random errors arising from the analysis (called analytical precision)
- 3) Systematic errors arising from the sampling (called sampling bias)
- 4) Systematic errors arising from the analysis (called analytical bias)

If errors from these sources are quantified, separately or in combinations, it is possible to estimate the uncertainty of the measurements that these methods produce.

Four empirical methods for estimating the combined uncertainty including the sampling are applicable:

- 1) Duplicates method allows to estimate the sampling precision and the analytical precision
- 2) Protocol method which uses method which uses one person for the sampling, a single protocol one person for the sampling and multiple protocols allows to estimate the sampling precision and the sampling bias between protocols, and the analytical
- 3) Collaborative trial in sampling (CTS) method which uses several persons for the sampling, a single protocol allows to estimate the sampling precision and the sampling bias between samplers, the analytical precision and the analytical bias
- 4) Sampling proficiency test (SPT) method which uses several persons for the sampling, and several protocols allows to estimate the sampling precision and the sampling bias between samplers and the protocols, the analytical precision and the analytical bias

2.2 Duplicates method

The duplicates method is the simplest and probably most cost-effective of the four methods. It is based upon a single person taking a small proportion (i.e., 10%, but no less than eight samples) of the primary

samples in duplicate (by repeating the same nominal sampling protocol). Ideally the duplicates are taken from at least eight sampling targets. If only one target exists, then all eight duplicates can be taken from it, but the uncertainty estimate will only be applicable to that one target. Each duplicate is analysed twice. This system of duplicated sampling and chemical analysis is known as a ‘balanced design’.

Typically, the balanced design for sampling at HRS if there is only one sampling target will be as shown on Figure 1:

Figure 1 - balanced design for one sampling target only

The balanced design for sampling at HRS if there are several sampling targets (at least eight, could be different stations with similar designs, inclusive the source for the hydrogen – water electrolysis for example) will be as shown on Figure 2.

To avoid mixing analytical uncertainty and sampling uncertainty, it is recommended to realise the analysis in repeatability conditions. The data treatment may use an analysis of variance to separate the uncertainty between duplicate (sampling uncertainty) from the uncertainty within duplicate (analysis uncertainty)

Figure 2 - balanced design for several sampling targets

Quantification of sampling precision and the analytical precision can then be made using normal or a robust analysis of variance (ANOVA or RANOVA) if outlying targets can be considered to be anomalies.

The sum of the squares and sigma values (variances) are calculated for between targets (if possible), sampling and analysis. For practical purposes, $\sigma = s$, so $\sigma_{\text{sampling}} = s_{\text{sampling}}$

$$s_{\text{measurement}} = \sigma (s_{\text{sampling}}^2 + s_{\text{analytical}}^2) \quad \text{equation 1}$$

$s_{\text{measurement}}$ can be used as an estimate of the random component of the standard uncertainty (u).

Applying the duplicate method can generally increase the cost of sampling by 10%, and the analysis by 30%. For assessment of hydrogen purity at HRS, as the cost of sampling is high, the added cost to use the duplicate method is much higher than the general increase. However, the sampling uncertainty may be estimated during the sampler commissioning through repetitive sampling. A current drawback is the difficulty to assess if the sample is truly representing the sample population.

Quantification of the sampling bias and the analytical bias is done using for example certified reference materials for the analysis and a reference sampling target or an inter-organisational sampling trial. The outcomes of task 3.3 (recommendation for the development of a real size metrological validation facility for HD-HRS) of MetHyTrucks project will provide information about how to obtain a reference sampling target.

2.3 Modelling approach

The modelling approach identifies all the sources of uncertainty, quantifies the contributions from each source, and then combines all the contributions, as a budget, to give an estimate of the combined standard uncertainty which is calculated by summing the uncertainty from all of the steps using a model that adds the variances.

2.3.1 Cause-and-effect modelling

The uncertainty of measurement generated by each of sources is estimated independently, either empirically or by other methods.

Uncertainty arises from a variety of sources, and these can be categorised in different ways. Eight major categories of have been identified, of which the first two are sampling and sample treatment.

For sampling, the sources of uncertainty have been identified as [8]:

- heterogeneity,
- effects of specific sampling strategies,
- effect of movement of medium, physical state,
- temperature and pressure effects,
- effect of sampling process on composition,
- transportation and preservation of the sample.

Close attention should be paid to minimising potential sources of bias. These include possible bias associated with differential sampling due to particle size, density or flow rate; bias in selection of sampling points; the effect of different sampling equipment etc. Specific expertise in sampling

methodology should be sought unless these factors can be demonstrated to be adequately controlled or are completely specified by an established sampling protocol.

For gas sampling, attention should be paid but not limited to the following technical aspects in order to collect sufficient representative sample [1].

- Adsorption, reaction and permeation of sampling system
- Leaks and atmospheric diffusion in the sampling system
- Purging of the sampling system
- Homogeneity of gas

2.3.2 Sampling theory

Sampling theory has been proposed as an appropriate method for estimating uncertainty from sampling [9] [7]. This approach relies on the use of a theoretical model, such as that of Gy. When Gy sampling theory is presented in the context of determining the level of an analyte (or a pollutant) in a lot, error usually refers to any deviation from the mean. The total sampling error (TE) can be defined as

$$TE = \frac{a_s - a_L}{a_L} \quad \text{equation 2}$$

where a_L is the actual (mean) content of the analyte in the lot and a_s is a measure of the (mean) content of the analyte in the sample (it is the sample estimator of a_L).

The figure 3 shows Gy's classification of sampling errors. However, it is worth mentioning that many of the sampling errors are applicable to solid and liquid samples.

Figure 3 - Gy's classification of sampling errors

$$GEE = TSE + TAE$$

$$TSE = (PSE + FSE + GSE) + (IDE + IXE + IPE) + SWE$$

Incorrect sampling errors arise from sampling equipment and procedures that do not follow the rules of sampling correctness defined in the sampling theory. In Figure 3, these errors are shown in shadowed boxes. The sources for the sampling uncertainty are shown in the table 1.

Table 1 - Incorrect sampling errors as described in the Gy sampling theory

Source	Description	Relevant examples
Fundamental sampling error	A result of the heterogeneity of composition (particles being chemically or physically different)	Sample composition random error
Grouping and segregation error	A result of the heterogeneity of distribution	Contaminant segregate due to molecular weight, density (i.e., CO ₂ or water versus H ₂) in a static tank
Long-range point selection error	Due to trends across space or time	Sampling from a dead volume section of a system

Periodic point selection error	Periodic levels across space or time	Sampling after a maintenance event for periodic monitoring
Increment delimitation error delimitation error (type of sampling / not sampling the process correctly)	Identify the correct sample to take. Consider the volume boundaries of a correct sampling device	Sampling during a refuelling event (parallel sampling) or from a specific storage bank (serial sampling)
Increment extraction error (sampling methodology or realisation)	While collecting the intended sample. Consider shape of the sampling device cutting edges	Sampling system not passivated (i.e., loss of reactive species) or not purged prior to sample taking (fake positive on O ₂ , N ₂ , water) Sampling with a prefilled cylinder without considering the dilution effect related to the exciting pre hydrogen in the sampling cylinder
Increment and sample preparation error (sampling container)	Contamination, losses (adsorption, condensation...), alteration of chemical composition (preservation), alteration of physical composition (breaking of particulates...) – very relevant for gaseous species Involuntary mistakes (lack of knowledge, negligence) Deliberate faults	Selective adsorption or breakthrough for thermos desorption sample preparation Type of cylinders used is capable of keeping the sample in its original state
Weighing error	Error in assigning weigh to different parts of an unequal composite sample	Not applicable for hydrogen fuel

The sampling device should be designed so that it can extract the intended sample profile, i.e., that all constituents have an equal chance to end up in the sample. Otherwise, sample or increment extraction error (IXE) is created.

When the incorrect sampling errors such as involuntary mistakes are eliminated, sampling errors can be modelled and used for estimating the uncertainty of sampling.

Fundamental sampling error (FSE) is the minimum error of an ideal sampling procedure. Ultimately it depends on the number of critical particles in the samples. For homogeneous gases and liquids, it is very

small but for solids, powders and particulate materials, especially at low concentrations of critical particles, fundamental error can be very large.

2.3.3 Uncertainty for particulate sampling

For particulate systems, sampling theory uses a similar approach to identifying seven types a sampling error. One of these errors (fundamental) is estimated using an equation based on a detailed knowledge of the individual particles being sampled:

$$\sigma_r^2 = C \cdot d^3 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{M_S} - \frac{1}{M_L} \right) \quad \text{equation 3}$$

Where:

σ_r is the relative standard deviation of the fundamental sampling error

D is the characteristic particle size = 95% upper limit of the size distribution

M_S is sample size

M_L is the lot size

C is the sampling constant that depends on the properties of the material sampled.

How to quantify the other errors is not detailed in the guide, only the concept of these errors is explained.

3 Size of the sample compared to the size of the lot

Very little information could be found about recommendation regarding the sample size in general and even less specifically for gas matrices. For particulates, the size of the sample is included in the equation used to estimate the fundamental sampling error and has a notable influence.

The discussion here focusses on calculating the size of the sampled compared to the size of the lot for some examples presented in the Eurachem guide "Measurement uncertainty arising from sampling".

In example A1 (nitrate in lettuces), a sampling target consists of up to 20000 lettuces (a bay). From this, a primary sample is collected (the primary sample consists of 10 heads, so min. 0,05% of the sampling targets is collected as primary samples). 50% of each head are combined and prepared to form one primary sample from which two samples (duplicates) are extracted. These two samples represent then much less 0,025% of the target samples.

In example A2 (lead in contaminated top soil), a sampling target consists of a surface of soil of 900 m². From this, a sample of 25 mm diameter is collected. This represents 0,00005% of the surface of the sampling target.

In example A4 (vitamin A in baby porridge), the uncertainties were measured fort wo different sizes of the sample (4 g, 1% of the package or 40-50 g, 10-12.5% of the package). Even through the package looks homogenous, the expanded measurements uncertainty was found to be almost 4 times higher with the sample of 4 g, showing that this sample weight is not "fit for purpose".

4 Methodologies to assess representativeness

Very few documents were found where methodologies to assess representativeness are described. However, one article published in the “Environmental Forensics” [4] tries to describe such a methodology.

The authors first point out that the term “representative” has many definitions. If a definition cannot be agreed on, it becomes difficult to evaluate representativeness in a meaningful way.

For the authors, determination of the representativeness of samples is not a matter of statistical analysis of the data after the fact [4]. It is a result of careful planning and proper design. The representativeness applies to the field sample as well as the subsample (sample that is actually analysed in the laboratory). The major components of assessing sample representativeness are:

Determining the data quality objectives

Are the question, population, and confidence clearly defined?

1. Evaluating sampling protocol design

Did the sampling protocol address both the compositional and distributional heterogeneity of the material

2. Evaluate sampling tools selection and use

Were the correct sampling tools used properly? Did the tools reach all parts of the available population? Did all portions of the population have the same probability of selection?

3. Evaluate Randomness and Accessibility

Was the sample collection random? Was the entire target population available for sample collection?

4. Evaluate Quality Control Data

Is there replication to determine errors of precision? Was the entire sampling scheme properly replicated? (The duplicates method can be applied here)

5. Final Evaluation of Field Sample Representativeness

If the plan does not pass any of the above criteria, the samples are not representative. Some of the criteria are pass/fail and others are compared to a standard, but all are critical.

5 Practical considerations

The validation of a sampling system is often complex compared to the validation of analytical methods for which validation parameters can be obtained through measurements on real samples and on reference materials. The first aspect to realise is sampling reference materials doesn't really exist or is extremely complex to achieve (i.e., accurately contaminating the whole hydrogen of a refuelling station to verify the ability of a system to collect a representative sample).

Therefore, the application of the empirical or duplicate approach will be preferably based on repeated measurements in real conditions. The advantage is the feasibility to realise such repetition due to existing infrastructure. However, one important drawback is the absence of contaminants in the hydrogen (hydrogen dispensed has been found in most of the cases to be very pure and to contain very few compounds above the thresholds in the quality standards). The empirical method will therefore only give information about the few compound(s) present above the limit of detection of the analytical methods. The actual nominal amount fraction in the hydrogen in the HRS storage needs to be considered knowing that the overall refuelling station parts may impact the composition (difference between storage and nozzle samples observed in 19ENG04 METroHyVe 2 project). It is important to determine the recovery yield which relies on knowing the amount fraction of all compounds in the system.

Therefore, applying the same approach used in inter-laboratory comparisons would allow to achieve a consensus value for all compounds sampled and provide equivalence between sampling systems. As all sampling is realised in reproducible conditions, it is the more appropriate situation that can be created to compare sampling systems. This is good approach for verifying sampling system in real life conditions at hydrogen refuelling stations. It has been applied with some success in 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 for light-duty sampling at HRS for four sampling systems.

Another challenge is related to the reactive compounds that are rarely or never found in real hydrogen samples even if they need to be analysed for hydrogen fuel quality assessment. The above proposed approaches will fail to provide any suitable information. In this case, the approach should rely on using reference gas cylinders with known amount fraction of contaminants and simulate a sampling event (or an event close to a refuelling event). It would allow to determine the agreement between the reference gas cylinders and the samples taken. It would provide some insight on the ability of the system to correctly sample the reactive compounds. Such realisation may be limited by the difficulty in simulating refilling conditions (T, P, flow) however it can be used as an indicator of suitability of the systems.

The last challenge is related to dynamic events (i.e. refilling) and variation of parameters during the events (storage bank, temperature) which will influence the final sample. It may be important to identify the limitation of the sampling methodology in such events: is the sample realised during the whole dynamic event? Was the sample taken homogeneously over the duration of the event? Does the sampling system follow the dynamic realisation?

It may be important to set boundaries and define assumption for each sampling system. For example, a direct sampling system will realise a sampling while the HRS is in maintenance mode, therefore it may sample only from one storage bank and not the whole system. In that case, the assumption is that all storage banks have equivalent hydrogen fuel quality. Another example is for parallel sampling which is realised during a refuelling event, the assumption in that case is that the hydrogen sample taken is distributed homogeneously across the refilling (same proportion from beginning to end of the event or biased toward fast filling at the beginning and slower filling as pressure equilibrates).

These practical considerations are critical to investigate in order to ensure that sampling methodologies are validated and representative.

6 Conclusion

This report discussed the term representativeness and a methodology proposed in Forensics science to assess sample representativeness, which is not based on statistical analysis of the data after the fact. In summary, representativeness is considered as a concept and not quantifiable.

The report also attempts to summarize the most relevant information from the Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide on measurement uncertainty arising from sampling. The aim of this Guide is to explain the rationale, and practical application, of the methods available for the estimation of uncertainty that include the contribution from sampling. Two main contributions to the sampling uncertainty need to be assessed: the sampling precision (due to random errors) and the sampling bias (due to systematic errors). In contrast to sample representativeness, measurement uncertainty is a quantitative notion.

There are two main approaches to uncertainty estimation arising from sampling; the empirical approach which uses some level of replication of the whole measurement procedure to give a direct estimate of the uncertainty for the final result of the measurement, and the modelling approach which identifies all of the sources of uncertainty, quantifies the contributions from each source, and then combines all of the contributions, as a budget, to give an estimate of the combined standard uncertainty.

Some indications on how to apply both methods are then given. Next steps will be to use this information in specific cases related to the sampling of hydrogen at heavy-duty refuelling stations.

Using the guideline on sampling for the measurement of gaseous impurities (A3.1.2) and the guideline on sampling for the measurement of particulate impurities (A3.1.3) that will be produced later on during the MetHyTrucks project, information collated in this report will be used to produce final comprehensive guidelines for representative sampling at HD-HRS, including the minimum sample size, the filling pressure and the evaluation of the uncertainty (target 10 % relative).

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